

The Application of Activity Based Costing Model to Calculates The Unit Cost Services In a Hospital

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Abstract— For welcoming the era of Universal Coverage in 2019, Indonesia has encouraged hospitals to be able to determine their service costs properly without being distorted, as happened in traditional costing models. This study aims to examine service costs in hospitals based on the Activity Based Costing method. The accurate calculation of the costs will encourage fair tariffs for patients and other payers, such as BPJS or other health insurance. The results of this study show that the service costs in the ORIF surgery of Femoral Shaft Fracture based on the calculation of the unit cost using the ABC method are about 10% lower than that based on the traditional hospital's costing method. This study concludes that the ABC method provides a fairer calculation of service costs for patients, according to facilities, processes (treatment activities), and the use of resources during the treatment. Since this ABC method eliminates useless activities that can trigger more costs, effectiveness and efficiency can be achieved to support the cost control and quality control in hospitals.

Keywords— Activity Based Costing, Unit Cost, Costs of Health Services.

I. INTRODUCTION

In line with the Indonesian health roadmap that will enter the era of Universal Coverage in 2019 and the continuation of the case-mix-based payment system (INA-CBG's), it is essential for hospital management and even the government to understand and evaluate the effects of unit cost in hospitals so that the rates of health services charged to patients are accurate. Traditional costing method has been practiced to

ascertain the hospital rates but it still can't meet the expectations because they have deteriorated the right tariffs.

Several results of previous studies show that the ABC method is the most suitable method used for hospitals to replace the traditional methods as costs of health services determiner. This method has implemented complexity, variations, and specific features. The distinguishing feature of this method with the previous methods is the ability to properly diagnose costs and present non-financial performance information to improve performance, efficiency, and effectiveness (Marvin et al., 2005). This method also can diagnose and reduce indirect resources (Cooper and Kaplan, 1992).

The ability of the ABC method to determine the calculation of accurate unit cost has driven more than 20 percent of hospitals in the US and Canada to use this method in the 1990s (Aryeh et al., 2008).

Several studies have shown the success of the ABC method in calculating the service costs in some hospitals in some countries, such as Turkey (Popesco and Novak, 2011), Japan (Cao Toyabe and Akazawa, 2006), Taiwan (Lin et al, 2007), India (Gujrat et al, 2010), Spain (Gonzales, Quesada, Mmack and Urrutia, 2005), Brazil (de Cavalho Jerico and Castilho, 2010), Argentina (Mrateu et al., 1998) America (Saneel Udpa, 1996), Sweden (Ridederstolpe, Johansson, Skau, Rutberg and Ahlfeldt, 2002), and Iran (Rajabi and Dabiri, 2012; Javid, Hadian, Ghaderi, Ghaffari and Salehi, 2016).

Therefore, it will be interesting to study the unit cost of health in hospitals supported by the Muhammadiyah organization. This because the Muhammadiyah organization has numerous

hospitals scattered throughout Indonesia. Therefore, the calculation of unit cost becomes an important issue. The results of this study aimed to see the difference between the unit cost calculated using the ABC method from the results of this study and the real cost calculation of the hospitals using a traditional costing method.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Empirical Research on The ABC Method in Hospitals*

There are two objectives of the ABC method based costing. The first is to prevent the occurrence of cost distortions as they usually occur with traditional costing methods. The second is to minimize activities that do not have added value by presenting the processes.

Suneel Udpa (1996) states that traditional costing systems in hospitals will provide a report of distorted costs because the overhead costs per patient per day are assumed to be the same regardless of the types of patient, the level of treatment, treatment procedures, or the length of stay.

Many studies show the superiority of the ABC method in the hospital industry. For example, research conducted by Lin et al. (2005) has found out how the ABC method in teaching hospitals was able to accurately calculate costs and identify several missing components before and after the surgery of a treatment.

Popesko and Novak (2005) show that this ABC model can give additional information that is not provided by traditional models. Therefore, decisions made based on this information can result in better cost efficiency, reduce waste, and improve negotiations on insurance costs.

Arnaboldi and Lapsley (2005) have tried to test a case in a UK health organization by applying the ABC method in hospitals. The study shows that several factors influence the successful implementation of the ABC method, such as the support from the top management, the company strategy and resources, the external consultants, the team size and diversity, the environment of competition, the training, and the interaction with the existing system.

Gonzales et al. (2005) has used Quality Function Deployment (QFD) in developing the ABC model. The results of their research imply

that the strategic decision-makers of hospitals could determine the basis of their decisions based on the appropriate allocation of time, people, and capital resources.

Similarly, De Carvalho Jerico and Castilho (2009) have carried an informative case study of the ABC method. The results of the study show that the information provided by the ABC method can optimize the entire understanding of the cost driver process and provide a basis for evaluating the performance improvement of the sterile processing department (SPD).

Cao et al. (2006) developed the Simplify ABC method (S-ABC) to reduce the workload of the ABC method. The results show that the S-ABC model can provide accurate estimation results that are the same as the accuracy of the ABC method.

Ridderstolpe et al. (2002) used a model for analyzing the ABC method as an information tool for administrative costs, decision-making strategies, quality improvement, and cost reduction. They conclude that the process of devising process-based costs can be applied, and it is potentially widely useful in hospitals.

Cannavacciuolo et al. (2014) examined the integration of the logic of the ABC method into the existing accounting system in hospitals to identify inefficiencies related to Diagnostic Therapeutic Pathways (DTP) and interventions. The results show how business process management and the ABC method could produce significant information about the consumption of resources and activity costs. Furthermore, the results of this study have been able to improve the process for the development of Diagnostic Therapeutic Pathways (DTP).

Water et al. (2001) examined the application of the ABC method to calculate the unit cost for hospitals in Peru. The results show that the application of the ABC method in developing countries has allowed us to generate results that could directly be applied to set prices (rates) and management.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. *Research Approach*

This was qualitative research with a case study form. The case study was chosen because the computation sample used a case of the ORIF of femoral shaft fracture in the surgery department in the research location.

B. Population and Sample

The population of this study was all patients who underwent the femur fractures treated in the research location. The sample of this study was the ORIF of the fracture of the femur (without any complication) patients. The patient fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria was selected as an example of the cost calculation and was chosen by the researcher when conducting observations in the Central Surgery Installation (CSI) of the hospital. The inclusion criteria is the ICD-10-CM entry and exit diagnosis: S72 Femur Fracture and the exclusion criteria are (1) The patient had multi-trauma requiring another operation than the diagnosis of Femur Fracture; (2) The surgery was stopped before it was finished due to the condition of the patient.

C. Data Analysis

This study used both primary data and secondary data. The primary data were collected directly from interviewing with orthopedic specialists, head of the central surgery installation, hospital finance department, administrative officer, and other parties. Furthermore, the researcher also directly observes the central surgery installation room to obtain data about the place and facilities available. The secondary data were records of the hospital, such as medical record data, clinical pathways, administrative records, hospital accounting and financial reports, and other documents. The steps of data analysis in this study divided into four major:

1. Using the primary and secondary data to identify and define activities
2. Listing the activities and actors of activities
3. Classifying the activities as primary activities and secondary activities and describing the tasks causing the activities
4. Identifying the cost driver to connect the main activity to the product

Based on the results of the primary and secondary data collection and the implementation of the steps above, the researcher could process the data of the direct and indirect costs that were the cost allocation of units through the following steps:

1. Determining the activity centers in the related units

2. Determining the cost and cost driver categories of each cost category
3. Charging the direct costs consumed on the ORIF of Femur Fracture services

Determining the costs of the direct resource overhead and indirect resource overhead consumed in each activity in the related units, namely Outpatient, Central Surgery Installation, Inpatient Ward, Emergency Installation, and Supporting Unit. Baker (1998) describes that these overhead costs are divided into 4 categories, namely:

- a. labor-related
- b. equipment-related
- c. space-related
- d. service-related.

D. Research Ethics

This research involved systems or institutions and individuals as the source of the data, research subjects, respondents, and so on. Therefore, the steps that could guarantee that this research did not harm the systems, institutions, or related individuals were needed.

IV. RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. The Center of Activities

Baker (1998) explains that an important reference for calculating the unit cost in a hospital is the Clinical Pathway procedure. As the reference for this study, the researcher used the Clinical Pathway for the ORIF of the Femoral Shaft Fracture adapted from the hospital. Then, based on the Clinical Pathway, the researcher could determine the center activities in the ORIF to calculate the unit cost, as shown in Table I. below.

TABLE I. THE CENTER OF THE ACTIVITIES IN THE ORIF OF FEMORAL SHAFT FRACTURE

The Location of Activities	The Center of the Activities	The First Stage of Cost Driver	The Second Stage of Cost Driver
Central Surgery Installation	Operating Room (Pre-operation)	Time	The number of activities
	Patient identification		
	The handover of the patient and the Medical Record		

The Location of Activities	The Center of the Activities	The First Stage of Cost Driver	The Second Stage of Cost Driver
	files		
	Checking the preparation for instruments and materials for the operation		
	Checking the pre operation list		
	Checking the preparation for anesthesia equipment and materials		
	Operating room durante the operation		
	Performing time in, durante, time out		
	Performing the procedure of anesthesia by an anesthesiologist		
	Performing the operation		
	Writing the operative report		
	Writing the post op instructions		
	Post-operative care room		
	Patient monitoring after the operation		
	The decision to leave the recovery room by an anesthesiologist		
	Calling the room to move the patient		
	The handover of the patient and the Medical Record		

The Location of Activities	The Center of the Activities	The First Stage of Cost Driver	The Second Stage of Cost Driver
	files		

After the central activity was identified, the steps to calculate the costs could be performed.

B. Charging the Direct Cost of the ORIF of Femoral Shaft Fracture

The direct cost of the ORIF of Femoral Shaft Fracture procedures covers the costs of specialist services, instrument sterilization, instruments used in the procedures, consumables goods, and linen laundry with a total cost of \$552.00. The details of the costs can be seen in Table II below.

TABLE II. THE DIRECT COST OF THE ORIF OF FEMUR FRACTURE

Cost Category	Unit	Total Unit ^(a)	Unit Cost ^(b) (\$)	Total ^(c) (\$)
Central Surgery Installation service				
Orthopedist (Class 3 Specific Surgery)	Procedure	1	72.41	72.41
Anesthesiologist (Class 3 Specific Surgery)	Procedure	1	36.21	36.21
Instruments (Broad DCP 8 hole&Cortical Screw No, 28-32: 8 pieces)	Equipment	1	365.55	365.55
Instruments Sterilization	Equipment	1	2.19	2.19
Laundry	Kg	4.8	0.41	1.99
Costs for consumpti\$n/surgery	Package	1	3.45	3.45
Drugs and Consumables				79.20

Cost Category	Unit	Total Unit (a)	Unit Cost (b) (\$)	Total (c) (\$)
Goods				
Total				552.00

*\$1 equal to Rp.14,500

C. *Calculating the Costs of Indirect Resource Overhead and Direct Resource Overhead Consumed by Each Activity*

According to Baker (1998), Overhead costs can be divided into two, namely indirect resource overhead cost and direct resource overhead cost. These overhead costs can then be grouped into four categories. They are labor-related, related equipment, space-related, and service-related.

1) *Calculating the indirect resource overhead cost of the hospital using the ABC method.* This is not an easy task. This because the business conditions of that have high variations of products (treatments) with low volumes that require customization.

TABLE III. THE INDIRECT RESOURCE OVERHEAD COST OF THE HOSPITAL

The Indirect Resource Overhead Cost	Cost (\$)
Labour related	
Employee cost	874,760.22
Equipment related	
The depreciation costs for furniture, office equipment, machinery, and installations	49,434.04
Spaced related	
The maintenance, reparation, and depreciation costs of nonfunctional buildings	
Service related	
The costs of procurement goods, office costs, and subscription fees	6,723.06
Total	947,587.98

*\$1 equal to Rp.14,500

From Table III. above, the indirect resource overhead cost of the hospital is \$947,587.98. It will be charged to each unit in the hospital according to the cost driver, such as the number of employees, the length of stay, and the number of the patient.

2) *Calculating the Direct Resource Overhead Cost*

The estimation of the direct resource overhead cost is applied to performed functional units. In this case, the service unit of the ORIF surgery of Femoral Shaft Fracture is the Central Surgery Installation.

TABLE IV. THE INDIRECT RESOURCE OVERHEAD COST OF THE HOSPITAL

The Direct Resource Overhead Cost in Central Surgery Installation (CSI) Unit	Cost (\$)
Labour related	
Employee cost	49,741.83
Equipment related	
The depreciation costs of medical and non-medical equipment in the CSI unit	112,141.79
The costs of equipment and building maintenance in the CSI	547.74
Spaced related	
The depreciation costs for nonfunctional buildings	33,347.02
Service related	
The cost of using procurement goods	89,101.56
Electricity cost in the CSI unit	10,520.59
Water cost in the CSI unit	7.55
Telephone cost in the CSI unit	264.31
Cleaning cost in the CSI unit	1,307.12
Total	297,006.52

*\$1 equal to Rp.14,500

Table 4. above shows that the Central surgery installation unit receives the direct resource overhead of \$297,006.52. This value will charge to all patients in the Central Surgery Installation based on the type of surgery. This because the hospital has applied a financial accounting system to calculate the costs of surgery based on the difficulty of the surgery, where the ORIF procedure of Femoral Shaft Fracture is categorized as a specific surgery.¹

¹ The charge is determined based on the table below:

Type of Surgical Procedure	The Number of Procedures	Point of Charge
Minor Surgery	3	0.5
Medium Surgery	579	1
Major Surgery	556	1.5

Thus, the direct resource overhead in the Central Surgery Installation is \$29,807.12 ((945x2/2511x7.5) x 297,006.52). Furthermore, the direct resource overhead for each specific surgery is \$ 31.54 (\$29,807.12/945 (the number of special operations)). Consequently, the direct resource overhead in the Central Surgery Installation is \$29,807.12 ((945x2/2511x7.5) x 297,006.52). Furthermore, the direct resource overhead for each specific surgery is \$ 31.54 (\$29,807.12/945 (the number of special operations)).

D. Counting the Direct Cost and Overhead Cost

The last part in calculating the unit cost is counting up all costs, both the direct cost and the overhead cost, of the ORIF surgical service of the Femoral Shaft Fracture. The result of the calculation is \$597.09 as shown in Table V. below.

TABLE V. THE UNIT COST OF THE ORIF OF FEMUR FRACTURE IN PKU MUHAMMADIYAH BANTUL HOSPITAL IN 2013

Cost Structure	Cost (\$)		
	Indirect Resource Overhead	Direct Resource Overhead	Total Overhead
The overhead cost of the ORIF of Femur Fracture in the Central Surgery unit	13.55	31.54	45.09
Direct cost			552.00
Total Cost			597.09

*\$1 equal to Rp.14,500

E. Discussion

The unit cost calculated using the ABC method for the ORIF surgery of Femur Fracture is as much as \$597.09. On the other hand, based on the hospital tariff calculated using a traditional accounting method, this will be worth \$655.58. These hospital costs are charged for room rental, operator, anesthesia and assistance, drugs and consumables, and

Specific Surgery	945	2
Advanced Surgery	428	2.5
Total	2.511	7.5

equipment. The difference between the hospital costs calculated using the traditional costing method and the ABC method in this study is \$58.49, or around 10% as shown in the Table VI. below.

TABLE VI. THE COMPARISON BETWEEN THE TARIFF METHOD AND UNIT COST USING THE ABC METHOD OF THE RESEARCH

Types of Cost	Unit Cost using the ABC Method (\$)	Cost of Service With the Tariff Method (\$)
Services in the Central Surgery Unit		
Indirect resource overhead	13.55	-
Direct resource overhead	31.54	-
The ORIF procedure of Femoral Shaft Fracture covering the costs of operator, anesthesia and assistance, and room rental	-	219.83
Direct cost :		
Drugs and consumables goods	79.20	79.20
The ORIF procedure of Femoral Shaft Fracture	72.41	-
The procedure of anesthesia	36.21	-
Laundry	1.99	-
Sterilization of instruments	2.19	-
Employee consumption cost	3.45	-
Instruments (pin, plate, screw)	365.55	365.55
TOTAL COST	597.09	655.58

*\$1 equal to Rp.14,500

Table VI. above proves that the ABC method can provide more accurate statements on service costs than the traditional scheme. Aforementioned can be seen from the way the

ABC method detailing the measures of resource consumed during each activity production.

Fig. 1. Example of a figure caption. (figure caption)

The most expensive cost in the case of surgery in this research is the cost for instrument (pin, plate, screw, etc.) Which covers 59,71% of the total costs. The percentage of the costs is shown in the pie chart above.

This ABC method provides an overview of fair costs for patients according to the facilities received and the resources used. This method can reduce unnecessary costs and effectively reduce costs that do not add value to the services based on the analyses of the activities. The ABC method will provide information to optimize resources and link costs and performance as well as the outcome.

Baker (1998) states that based on the ABC method, policymakers can use the ABC system information to improve efficiency without causing negative impacts on the quality of services and can also sustainably improve the quality of services. Therefore, the ABC method is the most suitable method to be used by hospitals in Indonesia because this method is following the current BPJS (Social Security Agency) era. Hospitals must be able to carry out quality control and cost control in providing health services to patients. Moreover, this

model provides good information in determining the costs of health services by a hospital to the patients.

V. CONCLUSION AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The surgical services unit cost calculation in hospitals based on the ABC method provides better and more accurate cost information than traditional methods. The unit cost for the ORIF surgery of Femoral Shaft Fracture based on the ABC method in this research is 10% lower than the conventional hospital costing method.

The ABC method will reduce unnecessary costs and activities. It will increase effectiveness and efficiency without reducing service quality. Thus, this method is following the objectives of quality control and cost control in hospitals in the era of universal coverage. Furthermore, hospital policymakers can also measure the performance of health workers based on this ABC method. There are some inputs for policymakers in the future of BPJS (Social Service Agency) and universal coverage. It appears that the components of health services taking the highest costs with a percentage of 73% in the ORIF surgery are the instruments or equipment (pen, plate, and screw) and also the drugs and consumables. For that reason, the government or policymakers in the health system in Indonesia should consider a method to reduce these two components of health costs by shortening the existing distribution channels. It will cut the extra cost. The decrease in equipment costs, drugs, and consumables will reduce the costs of health services in Indonesia.

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